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Review Article

A Review On: Indian Traditional Shrub Tulsi

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ABSTRACT

An effort has been made to discuss the medicinal properties of tulsi in this review. The medicinal benefits of plants are seen to be as secure, affordable, and effective as their accessibility. The plants of the genus *Ocimum* are recognised as having medicinal use. Tulsi is a widely used medicinal plant in India. highly valued for its medical and therapeutic applications. The roots of tulsi have a number of therapeutic benefits, including seeds and leaves. The human body is the target of a variety of its effects. Due to its chemical composition, it is believed to have anti-aging and immunomodulatory properties in

INTRODUCTION

Many of the medications currently in use are derived from plants, which are one of the most significant sources of medicine. The medicinal uses of plants are as secure, affordable, and efficient as their accessibility. Among the plants with medicinal properties, those of the genus *Ocimum* and family *Lamiaceae*. Due of their ability for healing, *Lamiaceae* are crucial. There are two types of *ocimum sanctum*. i.e., green (Rama Tulsi) and black (Krishna Tulsi), their chemical components are comparable². *Ocimum sanctum* is widely distributed all of the Indian subcontinent is covered by *sanctum*, which can be found reaching as high as 1800 m. As far as the Himalayas and the Andaman and Nicobar Islands³ The Sanskrit term

“tulsi” signifies It holds a particularly significant place in Hindu culture as “the matchless one.”

Synonyms:

Geniosporum tenuiflorum (L.) Merr.

Lumnitzera tenuiflora (L.) Spreng.

Moschosma tenuiflorum (L.) Heynh.

Ocimum anisodorum F. Muell.

Ocimum caryophyllinum F. Muell.

Ocimum hirsutum Benth.

Ocimum inodorum Burm.f.

Ocimum monachorum L.

Ocimum sanctum L.

Ocimum scutellarioides Willd. Ex Benth.

Ocimum subserratum B. Heyne ex Hook.f.

Ocimum tomentosum Lam.

Ocimum villosum Roxb.

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Plectranthus monachorum (L.) Spreng.

Scientific information:

Kingdom	plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliophyta
Order	lamiales
Scientific Name	ocimum sanctum
Family	labiatae
Genus	Ocimum
Species	sanctum

Chemical constituents:

A ¼ cup of fresh holy basil leaves contains—:

- # calories : 1.38
- # proteins : 0.189 g
- # fat : 0.038 g
- # carbohydrates : 0.159
- # fiber : 0.096 g
- # sugar : 0.018 g

Fig 1: Major compounds present in *Ocimum sanctum*

EXTRACTION METHOD

It is a fragrant plant. Since the beginning of humankind, plants have provided sources of therapeutic compounds. Preparation of aqueous extract of ocimum sanctum (leaves)-:Using distilled water, it was possible to get significant amounts of the leaf extract. In this procedure, 200 ml of beaker were filled with 20 g of powdered ocimum sanctum leaves, and 100 ml of distilled water was added. The beaker was then left at room temperature for about 22 hours to allow for thorough mixing and the complete elucidation of the active materials to dissolve in the appropriate

solvent. Next, the extract was filtered using muslin cloth and Whatman no 1 filter paper, and the resulting green colour filtrate was obtained. The experiment was completed after the residues were collected.

Phytochemical screening:

Chemical tests were performed using an aqueous extract to detect various constituents using the proven techniques of Sofowara, Trease and Evans, and Harbone.

Tannins Testing:

A small amount of FeCl₃ and 2 ml of the aqueous extract were combined. A solution was added. The

development of a green precipitate was a sign that tannins were present.

Saponins tests:

In a test tube, 5 ml of the aqueous extract and 5 ml of heated distilled water were briskly shaken. It was thought that the development of stable foam was a sign of saponins.

Phlobatannins test:

Phlobatannins were checked by boiling a combination of 2 ml of the aqueous extract and 2 ml of 1% HCL. The accumulation of red precipitate was seen as proof of phlobatannin existence.

Flavonoids tests:

1 ml of a 10% lead acetate solution was added to 1 ml of the aqueous extract. The development of a yellow precipitate was regarded as a successful indicator of flavonoids.

Terpenoids test:

Chloroform was dissolved in 2 ml of the organic extract before being evaporated to dryness. 2 ml of Then, concentrated sulfuric acid was added, and the mixture was heated for roughly 2 minutes. Emergence of a greyish hue Displays terpenoids in the environment.

Tulsi plant according to Ayurveda :

All Tulsi plant components should be used, according to Ayurvedic experts (*Ocimum Sanctum*). To prepare its juice, we must gather Tulsi's leaves, tender branches, tender roots, seeds, and nearly all aerial parts. One of the Tulsi plants. With clear water running, thoroughly clean them. Crush them after cutting them into little bits. To prepare a soft paste, combine them in a mortar and pestle. Place the created arrangement on a cotton sheet. To obtain pure Tulsi fluid, press a towel over it. Tulsi is an ayurvedic medication, and plant extracts from the tulsi. Ayurvedic treatments for inflammation, heart disease, headaches, stomach problems, and the common cold, Malaria and different poisonings are also

common. Tulsi is typically consumed in a variety of ways, including as a herbal tea, Stale powder.

Uses:

1. Tulsi has got the great medicinal value. studies have also shown Tulsi to be effective for diabetes by reducing blood glucose levels.
2. The same study showed significant reduction in total cholesterol levels with Tulsi.
3. Rama Tulsi is the effective remedy for the severe acute respiratory syndrome.
4. Tulsi oil is used as the ear drop.
5. Tulsi helps in curing malaria.
6. Tulsi is specially effective in supporting the heart, blood vessels, liver, and lungs and also regulates blood pressure and blood sugar.
7. For over the centuries Tulsi (the queen of herbs) has been known for its remarkable healing properties.
8. The fresh leaves of Tulsi are taken by millions of people everyday.
9. It is very effective against indigestion, headache, hysteria, insomnia and cholera
10. Tulsi improves the bodies overall defence mechanism including its ability to fight viral diseases.

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